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**A STUDY ON FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG RURAL PEOPLE
IN TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT**

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Abstract

Financial literacy plays an important role in financial education and inclusion. Financial education provides the awareness on various financial products and services that are available. Rural areas are those areas where there are no proper modern facilities and the population is comparatively lower than the cities. Rural people are mostly uneducated and are involved in agricultural, farming, livestock rearing etc. Due to lack of proper financial knowledge they are being guided by officials of particular village with respect to their money handling, savings, investments etc. Therefore to improve financial literacy in India especially in rural areas various strategies are being implemented by the government such as financial education in government schools and financial training programs in educational institutions in rural areas. Rural area people are being cheated by money lenders as they lack financial knowledge and are not capable of handling their finance. This will affect the household as well as

our economy as a whole. Financial awareness and proper knowledge is very important to all people especially people in rural areas. Rural people should be able to handle their own household budget, day to day expenses and their savings to tackle the emergency financial needs. Particularly in rural areas there are lot of financial malpractices and fraudulent activities that happens very frequently. This is due to lack of financial literacy and information among those people. Financial literacy provides effective financial awareness to use the financial resources to improve their wealth and security. The aim of this study is to know the financial literacy level among the rural people in Tirunelveli District.

Key Words: Financial Literacy, Financial Inclusion, Rural, Economic.

INTRODUCTION

More than 50% of our Indian population live in Rural areas. Rural people are engaged in the field of agriculture and other related occupations. Financial literacy in rural areas is very low compared to urban areas. Financial education is very important for rural people. Financial literacy requires proper knowledge of decision making in particular financial areas like real estate, saving, investing, insurance, tax planning, education and retirement. Financial literacy is gaining of knowledge and understanding of financial matters. Financial Literacy is very important for various reasons. Financial Literacy or education is to make one understand clearly about savings and their investments, money handling to take efficient decisions regarding ones financial resources. Now-a-days Financial literacy has been considered very important with regard to restrictions of financial markets and vary quick technological development of marketing financial products. Now-a-days variety of complex financial schemes for saving and borrowing, with multiple options are made available to consumers. To choose better option one should have better financial knowledge.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Problem of the study is to find out the financial literacy level of the rural people in Tirunelveli District.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the awareness of rural people in financial products and services
- To know how far the rural people are making wise judgment in saving and investment activities.
- To know the relation between various demographic factor (such as age, income, education, sex etc) with their Financial Literacy level
- To provide recommendations that help to improve financial literacy.

IV METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Data Analysis:

Primary data has been collected from 40 respondents within Tirunelveli Districts.

Type of Research:

An empirical study was done based on collection of data through questionnaire.

Sample:

Random sampling method has been adopted.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- **Anthes (2004)** has states that financial literacy is one of the ability to read, manage, analyze and communicate about the personal financial conditions which affects material well being.
- **Jariwala V. Harsha (2009)** has revealed in his study that all the respondents have invested their savings in various investment alternatives, despite majority of the respondents possess lower level of financial literacy.
- Worthington, 2006, there is no evidence that the low-income families are financial illiterate. Financial stress are related to various social problems like unemployment and poor economic conditions.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The framed questionnaire was asked from the people belonging to the rural areas of Tirunelveli District which includes 40 respondents. Apart from the demographic factors the questionnaire were asked based on the awareness of Financial Services and Financial literacy level.

Table 1 SOURCE OF FAMILY INCOME

Factors	Frequency	Percent
Income from Agriculture	9	22.5
Income from Spouse	6	15.0
Income from House hold work	12	30.0
Income from Live stock	7	17.5
Income from Job	6	15.0
Total	40	100.0

The table 1 explains that the source of income of family in rural areas are Income from house hold is 30% which is the highest source of income, Income from Agriculture is next major source of income with 22.5%, Income from live stock is 17.5% and income from Spouse and Jobs are 15% respectively. It reveals that majority of the income of respondents are from House hold activities.

Table 2 Knowing The Saving Habit

Factor	Frequency	Percent
Dont save	8	20.0
Atleast Once in a month	12	30.0
Once in a week	7	17.5
Like to save as and when I receive money	6	15.0
Once in six month	7	17.5
Total	40	100.0

Table 7 shows the savings habit of the rural people. 30% of the respondent prefer to save at least once in a month. 20% of them doesn't prefer to save. 17.5% of the respondent prefer save once in a week or once in six month. 15% of them prefers to save as and when they receive money. So majority of them prefer to save once in a month.

TO KNOW THE FINANCIAL LITERACY LEVEL OF THE RURAL PEOPLE.

The Literacy level of the rural people are measured on the basis of their demographic factor that's is on the Income of their family.

Table 3 Insurance Literacy Level

FACTOR	Low	Middle	High	Total	F
Timely help from insurance savings for sudden loss of a life.	3.80	3.29	3.75	3.40	.734
There are different policy available in insurance to save money.	2.80	3.45	3.50	3.38	.682
Insurance gives protection to life and also property.	1.20	2.84	4.00	2.75	7.285
Insurance companies are more trustable.	4.60	3.26	4.00	3.50	4.667
Children's plans are more beneficial and gives good return after long time.	2.60	3.03	3.25	3.00	.308
Rural people are not fear of future loss because of saving in insurance policies.	4.40	2.55	3.25	2.85	6.010

Table 8 shows Financial literacy level of the rural people. The low income group with highest mean value of 4.60 has highly agrees that Insurance companies are more trustable. The High income group people with mean value of 4 highly agree as there are no fear of future loss in saving with Insurance. The Low income group with the mean value 3.80 has moderate opinions to save in insurance as there are timely help due to sudden loss of life. Low income group with mean value of 1.20 highly disagree that Insurance gives protection to life and property.

Table 4 Banking literacy level

FACTOR	Low	Middle	High	Total	F
Rural People are able to save their money safely in the banks.	5.00	3.74	4.00	3.93	1.919
The banks are supportive to give any information about banking services	2.80	3.45	3.50	3.38	.807
Banks have given rural people more value added services apart from loans and deposits	3.20	2.94	5.00	3.18	7.226
Banks always give preference to grant loans to people.	3.40	2.77	3.50	2.93	1.013
Credit card and debit card usage are well known by the rural people.	4.00	3.48	3.25	3.53	.310
Savings and investment Schemes offered by banks are more useful to the rural people.	3.20	3.35	4.00	3.40	.405
The rural people are treated property and respected by bank staffs.	4.60	3.00	4.25	3.325	5.969

Table 9 reveals that the High Income group with mean value of 5 highly agrees that bank provides bank more value added services. Also low income group with mean value of 5 highly agrees that saving in Banks provides more safety. The mean value of 2.77 among middle income group reveals that the respondent highly disagree with the bank that the bank prefer to grant loans to all peoples.

Table 5 Postal Literacy Level

FACTOR	Low	Middle	High	Total	F
Very convenient for saving as it is functioning in all villages.	4.80	3.58	1.00	3.48	11.040
It is also more convenient for small savings.	3.60	3.77	1.75	3.55	5.233
More trustable than banks and insurance.	5.00	3.23	3.75	3.50	4.723463
Schemes offered by post office are more attractive thn banks and insurance.	2.60	3.00	3.75	3.03	1.400814
No loan facilities by post office.	2.60	2.39	4.25	2.60	3.969307
Rural postal life insurance(RPLI) is very useful for rural people.	4.20	2.55	3.25	2.83	4.915158

Table 10 shows the financial literacy level of postal services. Among the low level income group of high mean value 5 ,the respondent highly agrees that saving in Post office is more trustable than Bank and insurance. Among high income group with mean value of 4.25 highly agreed with postal department does not provide loan facility.

FINDINGS

- The majority of the respondents are female.
- Majority of the respondents are Married.
- Majority of the respondents education were Primary school.
- Majority of the respondent were of the age group 21 to 40.
- The Majority of the respondents income were between Rs.5000 to to Rs.15000.
- Most of the respondents live in Joint Family.
- Majority of the Source of income of respondents are from House hold activities.
- Majority of the respondent didn't have minimum amount to open an account in Bank.
- Majority of the respondent availed loan from the Bank.
- The low income group with highest mean value of 4.60, highly agrees that Insurance companies are more trustable.
- The High Income group with mean value of 5, highly agrees that bank provides more value added services.
- The low level income group of high mean value 5 ,the respondent highly agrees that saving in Post office is more trustable than Bank and insurance.

SUGGESTIONS

- In order to increase the savings habit of the rural people bank has to reduce the minimum balance for rural people to open account and enjoy the services of bank.
- Rural people should be made available all existing financial services in their particular region by arranging workshops such as financial literacy programs.
- All government introduces "Jan DhanYojana" for the financial welfare should be made known to the rural people .
- The banks in the rural areas should be able to communicate in their local language so that the rural people can understand the financial information of the banks.

CONCLUSION

Financial literacy makes people aware of the banking rules and regulations ,banking schemes, Insurance and postal savings scheme etc .Financial literacy is the key factor of financial inclusion and treated as a twin pillars. Without proper Financial Knowledge rural people will be facing increasing risk of making poor financial decisions whih will put them in financial risks like insecure old age. Financial education plays an important role in sustainability of economic well being. Due to very low literacy level in rural areas ,rural people are not in a position to take apt financial decision in their personal life and family which simultaneously affect their financial freedom and sustainability. This research article has focused on financial literacy of rural people based on various demographic factor as well as the financial literacy level. Financial literacy is the skill which makes people understand the financial principles and to make effective decisions and judgments regarding the use of their money.

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